

The Open Energy Platform in NFDI4Energy

A collaborative Data Infrastructure for Energy, Climate, and Mobility Research

Ludwig Hülk¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6234-0751>,
Christian Hofmann¹ <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-7207-9895>,
Mascha Richter¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2320-7808>,
Christian Winger² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1720-2501>,
Mirjam Stappel^{3,4} <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8938-5204>,
Martin Glauer⁴ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8368-7658>,
Oliver Werth⁶ <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-7207-1005>,
Stephan Ferenz^{6,7} <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1881-9172>

¹ Reiner Lemoine Institut, Germany

² Öko-Institut, Germany

³ Universität Osnabrück, Germany

⁴ Otto-von-Guericke-Universität Magdeburg, Germany

⁵ Universität Paderborn, Germany

⁶ OFFIS – Institute for Information Technology, Germany

⁷ Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Germany

*Correspondence: Ludwig Hülk, Ludwig.huelk@rl-institut.de

Abstract

The Open Energy Platform (*OEP*) [1] is a modular, web-based infrastructure designed to support open, transparent, and reproducible energy system modelling. Developed as open-source software, it offers services from the Open Energy Family (*OEFamily*) that enable the standardized publication, documentation, and reuse of energy-related data, models, and scenarios [2]. This article presents the main services and outlines the technical and conceptual framework with the overarching aim of enhancing interoperability, improving data quality, and fostering collaborative research in the energy domain.

The core component of the platform is the Open Energy Database (OEDB), a collaboratively used relational database for openly licensed datasets [3]. It stores a wide range of datasets, including input and output data from various energy system models. The database is organized into 11 thematic topics relevant to the energy domain, along with two additional topics for work-in-progress and scenario-specific data (*model_draft* and *scenario*). Built-in data versioning ensures reproducibility and traceability by maintaining structured records of dataset changes over time.

The Open Energy Metadata standard (*OEMetadata*) ensures FAIR and high-quality metadata. Its associated editor, the *OEMetaBuilder*, supports the creation and editing of metadata records [4]. *OEMetadata* supports the comprehensive description of datasets with multiple resources (e.g. tables) and incorporates contextual information such as the research project, spatial and temporal coverage, data sources, licensing, and chronological provenance. The standard is based on the Frictionless Data Package¹ specifications, DCAT-AP 3.0² and the FAIR Principles³. It was designed with consideration of existing standards, including Dublin Core, INSPIRE, DataCite⁴, schema.org⁵, and PROV⁶. A badge system prioritizes the keys and measures completeness and quality. The developed Open Peer-Review Process (OPR) enhances reliability through community validation, feedback, and iterative improvements, ensuring transparency and trust.

The Open Energy Ontology (*OEO*) [5] is a domain ontology developed collaboratively to formally represent concepts and relationships relevant to energy system analysis. It is based on the Basic Formal Ontology (BFO), ensuring logical consistency and interoperability. It reuses and aligns with several established ontologies such as units of measurement, time, and geo-spatial references. Based on the *OEO*, the Open Energy Knowledge Graph (*OEKG*) enables standardized documentation of energy scenarios (Scenario Bundles) and models [6]. The Virtual Knowledge Graph (*OEVKG*) enables comparison of models and scenarios across datasets.

The Open Energy Academy provides Open Educational Resources (OER) on RDM in climate and energy systems modelling. As part of the OEP, it offers Courses, Tutorials, and Questions (FAQ) to support users in utilizing the platform effectively. It is hosted on GitHub Pages and built using MkDocs.

In NFDI4Energy, the OEP contributes established services and offers a basis for future applications by the energy research community [8]. Further developments and improvements of the platform are underway, such as the integration of NFDI base services, including identity access management and the terminology service. By consistently applying open licenses, the OEP fosters collaborative and sustainable research data practices in energy systems analysis and serves as a key data infrastructure for energy, climate, and mobility research.

Keywords: Open Energy Platform (OEP), research data management (RDM), Energy, NFDI4Energy, collaborative development, data infrastructure

Resources

- Open Energy Family. <https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform>
“The OEFamily is a dynamic collection of tools and information designed to support working with energy-related data.”

¹ <https://datapackage.org/>

² <https://www.dcat-ap.de/def/dcatde/3.0/spec/>

³ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁴ <https://datacite.org/>

⁵ <https://schema.org/>

⁶ <https://www.w3.org/2001/sw/wiki/PROV>

- Open Energy Platform (OEP). <https://openenergyplatform.org/>
"A web interface and central hub to access most of the modules, especially the community database and factsheets."
- Open Energy Metadata. <https://openenergyplatform.github.io/oemetadata/>
"The metadata standard for the energy domain."
- Open Energy Academy. openenergyplatform.github.io/academy/
"Open Educational Resources (OER) with Courses, Tutorials, and Questions (FAQ)."
- Open Energy Compendium. <https://openenergyplatform.github.io/organisation/>
"Documentation and Overview of the OEFamily framework"

Author contributions

Conceptualization: Ludwig Hülk

Software: Jonas Huber, Martin Glauer, Christian Winger, Adel Memariani

Writing - original draft: Ludwig Hülk

Writing - review & editing: All authors

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Funding

Funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK).

Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG).

The authors would like to thank the German Federal Government, the German State Governments, and the Joint Science Conference (GWK) for their funding and support as part of the NFDI4Energy consortium.

This work was supported by the German Research Foundation (DFG) project number 501865131 within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, www.nfdi.de).

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank all members, developers and users of the Open Energy Platform and Open Energy Family.

References

- [1] Förster, H., Emele, L., Winger, C., Hülk, L., Hofmann, C., Reder, K., Stappel, M., & Glauer, M. (2021). Abschlussbericht. SzenarienDB. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5509488>
- [2] Hülk, L., Glauer, M., Huber, J., & Winger, C. (2025). Open Energy Family - Open Energy Platform (OEP) (Version 1.2.2) [Computer software]. <https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/>

- [3] Hülk, L., & Huber, J. (2025). NFDI4Energy Conference 2025 - Service Poster - Open Energy Database (OEDB) (1.0). NFDI4Energy Conference, KIT Karlsruhe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15172633>
- [4] Hülk, L., & Huber, J. (2025). NFDI4Energy Conference 2025 - Service Poster - Open Energy Metadata Standard and the OEMetaBuilder (1.0). NFDI4Energy Conference, KIT Karlsruhe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15172681>
- [5] Booshehri, M., Emele, L., Flügel, S., Förster, H., Frey, J., Frey, U., ... & Stappel, M. (2021). Introducing the Open Energy Ontology: Enhancing data interpretation and interfacing in energy systems analysis. *Energy and AI*, 5, 100074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyai.2021.100074>
- [6] Hülk, L., & Huber, J. (2025). NFDI4Energy Conference 2025 - Service Poster - Scenario Bundles and Comparisons (1.0). NFDI4Energy Conference, KIT Karlsruhe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15172661>
- [7] Hülk, L., & Huber, J. (2025). NFDI4Energy Conference 2025 - Service Poster - Open Energy Academy (1.0). NFDI4Energy Conference, KIT Karlsruhe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15172590>
- [8] Nieße, A., Ferenz, S., Auer, S., Dähling, S., Decker, S., Dorfner, J., German, R., Gütlein, M., Hagenmeyer, V., Henni, S., Lehnhoff, S., Lilliestam, J., Lu, L., Mey, F., Monti, A., Muschner, C., Reinkensmeier, J., Richter, M., Schäfer, M., ... Zilles, J. (2022). nfdi4energy – National Research Data Infrastructure for the Interdisciplinary Energy System Research (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6772013>